

Oxygen Sensing by Arterial Chemoreceptors Depends on Mitochondrial Complex I Signaling

M. Carmen Fernández-Aguera,^{1,2,4,5} Lin Gao,^{1,2,4,5} Patricia González-Rodríguez,^{1,2,4,5} C. Oscar Pintado,³ Ignacio Arias-Mayenco,^{1,2,4} Paula García-Flores,^{1,4} Antonio García-Pergañeda,¹ Alberto Pascual,¹ Patricia Ortega-Saenz,^{1,2,4} and José López-Barneo^{1,2,4,*}

1. Instituto de Biomedicina de Sevilla (IBiS), Hospital Universitario Virgen del Rocío/CSIC/Universidad de Sevilla, Campus Hospital Universitario Virgen del Rocío, Avenida Manuel Siurot, s/n, 41013 Seville, Spain

2. Departamento de Fisiología Médica y Biofísica, Facultad de Medicina, Universidad de Sevilla, Avenida Sánchez Pizjuan, 4, 41009 Seville, Spain

3. Centro de Producción y Experimentación Animal, Universidad de Sevilla, Calle San Fernando, 4, 41004 Seville, Spain

4. Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red sobre Enfermedades Neurodegenerativas (CIBERNED), Campus Hospital Universitario Virgen del Rocío, Avenida Manuel Siurot, s/n, 41013 Seville, Spain

5. Co-first author

***Correspondence:** lbarneo@us.es

Abstract

O₂ sensing is essential for mammalian homeostasis. Peripheral chemoreceptors such as the carotid body (CB) contain cells with O₂-sensitive K⁺ channels, which are inhibited by hypoxia to trigger fast adaptive cardiorespiratory reflexes. How variations of O₂ tension (PO₂) are detected and the mechanisms whereby these changes are conveyed to membrane ion channels have remained elusive. We have studied acute O₂ sensing in conditional knockout mice lacking mitochondrial complex I (MCI) genes. We inactivated *Ndufs2*, which encodes a protein that participates in ubiquinone binding. *Ndufs2* null mice lose the hyperventilatory response to hypoxia, although they respond to hypercapnia. *Ndufs2*-deficient CB cells have normal functions and ATP content but are insensitive to changes in PO₂. Our data suggest that chemoreceptor cells have a specialized succinate-dependent metabolism that induces an MCI state during hypoxia, characterized by the production of reactive oxygen species and accumulation of reduced pyridine nucleotides, which signal neighboring K⁺ channels.

Introduction

The molecular mechanisms underlying acute O₂ sensing by cells are still to be elucidated. The discovery of the O₂-dependent prolyl hydroxylase-hypoxia inducible transcription factors pathway has provided a framework for understanding the genetic response to sustained (chronic) hypoxia (Kaelin and Ratcliffe, 2008; Semenza, 2012). However, acute O₂ sensing (with a time course of seconds) is necessary for the activation of rapid compensatory cardiorespiratory reflexes such as hyperventilation and sympathetic activation, which permit the survival of individuals under hypoxic environments (e.g., high altitude) or pathologic conditions with impaired gas exchange in the lungs (for review, see Lopez-Barneo et al., 2001). Acute responses to hypoxemia are mediated by activation of cells in the carotid body (CB) and other peripheral chemoreceptor organs (e.g., adrenal medulla [AM], pulmonary artery, or neuroepithelial bodies in the lung airways) forming the homeostatic O₂-sensing system (Weir et al., 2005; Nurse et al., 2006). CB O₂-sensitive glomus cells contain K⁺ channels whose inhibition by hypoxia leads to depolarization, Ca²⁺ influx, and transmitter release to activate nerve fibers conveying information to the respiratory center (Lopez-Barneo et al., 2001; Kemp and Peers, 2007). However, despite intense research, the molecular mechanisms underlying O₂ sensing by chemoreceptor cells have remained enigmatic. Mitochondria have classically been associated with acute CB O₂ sensing due to the exquisite sensitivity of glomus cells to electron transport chain (ETC) inhibitors and the close correlation between mitochondrial function and O₂ tension (PO₂) (Mills and Jobsis, 1970; Duchon and Biscoe, 1992; Buckler and Turner, 2013). Nonetheless, how mitochondria mechanistically respond to hypoxia to signal the glomus cell membrane has not been elucidated; therefore, several physiologically appealing alternative models of O₂ sensing have been proposed (reviewed by López-Barneo, 2003; Nurse et al., 2006; Evans et al., 2009; Prabhakar and Peers, 2014). Although all ETC inhibitors can impair O₂ sensing (Wyatt and Buckler, 2004), rotenone, a mitochondrial complex I (MCI) blocker, is particularly efficient at inhibiting CB glomus cell responsiveness to hypoxia without altering responsiveness to hypoglycemia (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2003; García-Fernández et al., 2007a).

We have tested the hypothesis that MCI participates in CB O₂ sensing by using several conditional genetically modified mice. In particular, we have inactivated the *Ndufs2* gene, which encodes a 49kDa protein contributing to the ubiquinone-binding site (quinone cage) of MCI (Kashani-Poor

et al., 2001; Grgic et al., 2004). This site is 7Å° from the distal Fe/S cluster (N2 center) in MCI; thus, electrons are transferred from the N2 center to ubiquinone during the last step in the NADH/ubiquinone oxidoreductase reaction. Rotenone binds to the inside of the quinone cage and prevents ubiquinone.

Results

Absence of HVR in TH-NDUFS2 Animals with Preservation of Chemoreceptor Cell Integrity

As biallelic genetic deletion of *Ndufs2* results in embryonic lethality, we engineered a floxed *Ndufs2* allele to induce an *Ndufs2* deficiency that is restricted to catecholaminergic cells (TH-NDUFS2 mice), which include the O₂-sensitive and tyrosine hydroxylase-positive (TH+) reduction (for the MCI structure, see Baradaran et al., 2013; Zickermann et al., 2015). Herein, we report that the reflex hypoxic ventilatory response (HVR) is completely abolished in animals lacking *Ndufs2*. Unexpectedly, CB glomus cells from these animals with altered MCI function have preserved morphology, electrophysiology, secretory activity, and ATP levels. However, they are insensitive to changes in PO₂, despite exhibiting normal responsiveness to other stimuli. We provide compelling functional and biochemical evidence suggesting a signaling role for MCI during hypoxia in cells of the peripheral chemoreceptors (CB and AM), thus providing insight into the mechanism of acute O₂ sensing. CB glomus and AM chromaffin cells as well as sympathetic superior cervical ganglion (SCG) neurons (Figures S1A–S1C). As our study focuses on peripheral chemoreception, an account on the effects of *Ndufs2* deletion on central catecholaminergic neurons will be given elsewhere. Newborn TH-NDUFS2 mice had a normal appearance and, although their weight gain was retarded after weaning, remained in apparently good condition until 2 months of age (Figures S1D and S1E). Under normoxic conditions (21% O₂), these animals had a basal breathing frequency that was similar to that in normal mice. However, whereas a rapid increase in ventilation was induced by hypoxia (10% O₂) in controls (Figure 1A), this characteristic HVR was absent in mutant animals (Figure 1B), which, in contrast, exhibited a normal ventilatory response to hypercapnia (Figures 1C and 1D). TH-NDUFS2 mice had a well-preserved CB, which even showed hypertrophy with a normal histological appearance (Figures 1E–1G). Nevertheless, electron microscope (EM) analyses demonstrated ultrastructural alterations in *Ndufs2*-deficient glomus cells, which contained fewer secretory vesicles and more mitochondria compared with controls (Figures 1H–1J). *Ndufs2* mRNA levels were significantly reduced in CB

tissue from TH-NDUFS2 mice (Figure 1K), although, surprisingly, the ATP content was unchanged or even increased (Figure 1L). As expected, MCI activity, measured in the SCG, was drastically decreased in catecholaminergic tissues of TH-NDUFS2 mice (Figure S1F). These data indicate that glomus cells, which are known to have a high O₂ consumption and metabolic rate, can survive without a functional MCI, suggesting that they must have a highly active succinate-dependent ubiquinone reduction pathway to synthesize ATP. Indeed, we have found that glomus cells contain high concentrations of succinate in comparison with other neural tissues (Figure 1M).

Selective Loss of Hypoxia Responsiveness by Ndufs2 Null Chemoreceptor Cells

The chemosensory responses of individual glomus cells from control and TH-NDUFS2 mice were studied by amperometry, microfluorimetry, and patch-clamp (see Experimental Procedures). Depolarization with high K⁺ evoked a characteristic strong exocytotic response that was quantitatively (secretion rate and mean vesicle content) similar in normal and Ndufs2-deficient CB cells (Figures 2A–2C). In CB slices, most of the control cells activated by high K⁺ also exhibited a burst of secretory activity of similar magnitude in response to hypoxia (PO₂ 15 mm Hg), hypercapnia (20% CO₂), or 0 mM glucose, which are sensory stimuli for chemoreceptor glomus cells (Lopez-Barneo et al., 2001; García-Fernández et al., 2007a; Zhang et al., 2007)(Figures S1G and 2D). In sharp contrast, glomus cells from TH-NDUFS2 mice were completely insensitive to hypoxia despite the fact that they had normal responsiveness to high K⁺ (Figures 2B and 2C), hypercapnia, and 0 glucose (Figure 2E). In normal animals, >90% of the high K⁺-sensitive cells responded to hypoxia, whereas in TH-NDUFS2 mice <15% of cells (Figure 2F) showed weak responses in comparison with controls (Figure 2G). In accord with the amperometric data, Fura 2-loaded dispersed glomus cells from control animals showed a characteristic rise in cytosolic [Ca²⁺] upon exposure to high K⁺, hypoxia, hypercapnia, or 0 mM glucose. With the exception of the response to hypoxia, which was practically abolished, these responses were maintained in cells from Ndufs2-deficient mice (Figures 2H–2K). Resting cytosolic [Ca²⁺] was similar in control (102 ± 10 nM, n = 80 cells) and TH-NDUFS2 (109.9 ± 3.3 nM, n = 160 cells) mice (n = 7).

Next, we examined whether modulation of K⁺ channels by PO₂, the primary event that determines the chemosensory properties of glomus cells (for review, see Lopez-Barneo et al., 2001), is altered in Ndufs2-deficient CB cells. Apart from a nonsignificant decrease in Ca²⁺ channel density, voltage-dependent currents were similar in whole-cell patch-clamped control and mutant glomus

cells (Figures S2A–S2F). We used the perforated-patch technique to apply ramp depolarizations from 90 to -10 mV) to single cells. A linear holding current (mediated by “background” channels) was recorded between -90 and -50 mV, which was followed at more depolarized membrane potentials by a large outward current due to the activation of voltage-gated K⁺ channels. With this protocol, voltage-dependent inward Na⁺ and/or Ca²⁺ currents were relatively small (Figures 3A and 3B). Consistent with the findings obtained with amperometry and Ca²⁺ microfluorimetry (see Figure 2), hypoxia produced a reversible inhibition of the voltage-dependent and “background” (measured as an increase of membrane resistance) K⁺ channels, which was abolished in *Ndufs2*-deficient cells (Figures 3A–3D). Hypoxic inhibition of outward K⁺ currents elicited by depolarizing pulses was also selectively abolished in *Ndufs2* null cells (Figures S2G–S2J). Taken together, these data indicate that glomus cells from TH-NDUFS2 mice exhibit a complete but selective loss of sensitivity to changes in PO₂, which explains the absence of HVR in the whole animal. In normoxic conditions, mutant cells showed a distinct electrophysiological phenotype characterized by a decrease in the holding current (almost a 5fold increase in input resistance) (Figures 3E–3G) and a shift of the reversal potential to depolarized values in comparison with controls (Figure 3E; Table S1). A standing inward Na⁺ current, characteristic of glomus cells (Carpenter and Peers, 2001; García-Fernández et al., 2007a), was unchanged (Table S1). These data thus indicate that the lack of MCI activity in *Ndufs2* null cells results in a strong “hypoxic” phenotype with inhibition of K⁺ channels. Indeed, in support of this concept, mutant cells displayed a more depolarized resting membrane potential (15 mV) than control cells (Table S1). The partial degranulation noted in the EM studies described above (see Figures 1H–1J) is also indicative of a chronic activation of these cells. These changes could explain CB hypertrophy in TH-NDUFS2 mice due to activation of the glomus cell-stem cell “chemoproliferative” synapse (Platero-Luengo et al., 2014). In addition to TH-NDUFS2, we studied two other mitochondrial mutants to investigate the sensitivity of glomus cells to changes in PO₂. Using animals containing a floxed *Ndufs4* allele (Kruse et al., 2008), we generated the TH-NDUFS4 mouse. *Ndufs4* encodes an accessory protein located in the peripheral arm of MCI that has no catalytic role but is required for assembly or stabilization of the complex. Systemic inactivation of this gene results in encephalomyopathy and other alterations due to an inhibition of NADH oxidoreductase activity and a 60% decrease in MCI-dependent O₂ consumption (Kruse et al., 2008). CB from TH-NDUFS4 mice nevertheless appeared normal, although, as the equivalent in TH-NDUFS2 animals

(see Figure 1K), it showed a selective decrease of *Ndufs4* mRNA in catecholaminergic cells (Figures S3A–S3C). However, *Ndufs4*deficient glomus cells exhibited a robust secretory response to hypoxia and other stimuli (Figures S3D and S3E), thus further suggesting a selective association of the MCI ubiquinone oxidoreductase activity with acute O₂ sensing. To rule out the possibility that the inhibition of acute CB O₂ sensing in the TH-NDUFS2 mice was a consequence of a developmental alteration, we generated heterozygous (*Ndufs2* f/-) animals with ubiquitous expression of Cre recombinase activated by tamoxifen (TMX) (ESR-NDUFS2 mice). These mice developed normally and were used for experiments at 4 months of age; that is, 7 weeks since the beginning of TMX treatment, but before they died due to pleiotropic organ failure. Wholebody plethysmography revealed the disappearance of the acute HVR in TMX-treated ESR-NDUFS2 mice (Figures S4A–S4C). These animals exhibited a normal CB structure, despite having a marked decrease in *Ndufs2* mRNA (Figures S4D–S4F). Analyses of single CB cell responsiveness to hypoxia demonstrated a loss of O₂ sensitivity in adult *Ndufs2*-deficient glomus cells, even though they maintained normal responses (catecholamine release) when challenged with high K⁺, hypercapnia, or 0 mM glucose (Figures S4G–S4K).

Although less sensitive than glomus cells, adult chromaffin cells in the AM also display chemoreceptive properties and can release catecholamines in response to hypoxia and hypercapnia (Thompson et al., 1997; Muñoz-Cabello et al., 2005; Nurse et al., 2006; García-Fernández et al., 2007b). In contrast to the CB, the number of chromaffin cells decreased in the TH-NDUFS2 mice (Figures 4A and 4B) with a significant decrease of ATP (Figure 4C). As the AM is larger than the CB, we could show the parallel decrease in *Ndufs2* mRNA and protein in this preparation (Figure 4D). Amperometric recordings in AM slices from wildtype mice showed typical increases in secretory activity induced by hypoxia, hypercapnia, and high (20 mM) K⁺. In contrast, all chromaffin cells from TH-NDUFS2 mice were insensitive to hypoxia, although they exhibited normal responsiveness to hypercapnia and high K⁺ (Figures 4E–4I). Similar selective loss of sensitivity to hypoxia was observed in chromaffin cells from ESR-NDUFS2 mice (Figures S5A–S5H). These findings suggest that, as in CB glomus cells, acute O₂ sensing in AM chromaffin cells also depends on *Ndufs2* function.

Mitochondrial Function and Abolition of Acute O₂ Sensing in Ndufs2-deficient Cells Respiring with Succinate

The impact of Ndufs2 deficiency on MCI function was investigated in detail in kidney cells of ESR-NDUFS2 mice using blue native gels, Western blot, and mitochondrial activity/respiration analyses, as these studies are not feasible on small organs such as the CB or AM. Ndufs2 deletion resulted in a marked decrease of Ndufs2 mRNA and protein (Figures S6A and S6B) and almost complete disappearance of the assembled MCI, as evidenced by antibodies against proteins in the peripheral (Ndufs2, Ndufs1, and Ndufv2) and membrane (mtNd1) arms (Figure 5A). The decrease of MCI proteins in the whole-cell protein extracts or subcellular protein fractions from kidney of ESR1NDUFS2 mice compared to their control littermates suggests that Ndufs2 deficiency induces a degradation more than a cytoplasmic accumulation of the non-assembled proteins (Figures S6C and S6D). Antibodies against mtNd1 detected a high molecular weight (similar to that of MCIII) protein complex in Ndufs2-deficient cells that was compatible with the preassembled membrane arm of MCI, although it seemed to include some proteins of the peripheral arm (sub I in Figure 5A). As expected, MCI NADH/ubiquinone oxidoreductase activity (Figure 5B) and MCI-dependent O₂ consumption (Figures 5D–5F) were practically abolished in mitochondria from ESR-NDUFS2 mice. Mitochondrial complex II, III, and IV proteins were unaltered or even slightly upregulated in Ndufs2null cells (Figures 5A and S6B). As a result of that, MCII activity (Figure 5C) and O₂ consumption in the presence of succinate (Figure 5F) were normal with respect to control values. In the presence of succinate, Ndufs2-deficient mitochondria seemed to respire well through the complex IIIIV pathway (Figures 5E and 5F); therefore, we investigated whether allowing Ndufs2-deficient glomus cells to respire with succinate, and consequently bypassing MCI, would lead to the recovery of sensitivity to changes in PO₂. Glomus cells from control and TH-NDUFS2 mice cultured in medium containing 2 mM methyl succinate (to favor membrane permeability) plus 2 mM succinate salt were healthy and exhibited the characteristic rise in cytosolic [Ca²⁺] in response to high K⁺, 0mM glucose, or hypercapnia. However, responsiveness to hypoxia, unaffected in controls, remained completely abolished in Ndufs2-deficient cells (Figures 5G–5I). These data indicate that Ndufs2 is necessary for the full assembly of MCI and that in arterial chemoreceptors MCI is essential for signaling to membrane K⁺ channels during acute hypoxia.

Mitochondrial Complex I Signaling to Membrane K⁺ Channels in Response to Hypoxia

We hypothesized that the inhibition of membrane K⁺ channels and depolarization characteristics of glomus cells from TH-NDUFS2 mice (Figures 3E–3G; Table S1) were due to the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by preassembled MCI subcomplexes (Figure 5A) with residual NADH oxidoreductase activity but without ubiquinone-reducing site. We therefore tested the effect of buffering intracellular ROS with small concentrations of N-acetylcysteine (NAC; 25–50 mM) added to the recording pipette. Dialysis of *Ndufs2*-deficient cells with NAC produced a marked decrease in input resistance (seen as an increase in holding current), which reached values similar to those found in normal cells (Figure 6A). NAC had no obvious electrophysiological effects on control cells; however, dialysis of these cells with an oxidizing agent (H₂O₂, 15–50 mM) resulted in a marked increase in input resistance that was characteristic of the “hypoxic” phenotype (Figure 6B). A 2.5fold increase in input resistance was also observed in cell dialyzed with diamide (50–60 mM), a thioloxidizing agent (Figures S7A–S7D). Although NAC-dialyzed *Ndufs2* null cells recovered a normal input resistance value, they remained insensitive to hypoxia (Figures 6C, top; 6D; and 6E). On the other hand, the modulation of background K⁺ current by hypoxia (Figures 3A–3D) was abolished in control cells dialyzed with either H₂O₂, diamide, or NAC (Figures 6F, S7B, and S7C). As the hypoxic modulation of voltage-gated currents was barely affected by low levels of H₂O₂, diamide, or NAC (Figures 6C, bottom; 6G; S7B; and S7D), we tested higher intracellular concentrations of redox agents; however, under these conditions, the recordings were unstable. Being established that several background and voltage-gated K⁺ channels are susceptible to intracellular redox modulation (Bychkov et al., 1999; Papreck et al., 2012; Sahoo et al., 2014), these data suggested that inhibition of MCI and the subsequent local increase of ROS (O₂ and/or H₂O₂) during hypoxia is a signal that inhibits K⁺ channel activity in chemoreceptor cells. The role of ROS on O₂ sensing by peripheral chemoreceptors has been little explored (see López-Barneo, 2003; Thompson et al., 2007), and the effects of intracellular dialysis of ROS on background K⁺ currents in glomus cells have not been studied previously. However, changes in ROS production of mitochondrial origin have been classically proposed to participate in acute hypoxic vasoconstriction of pulmonary resistance arteries (Archer et al., 1993; Waypa et al., 2001) and in the closure of the ductus arteriosus after birth (Michelakis et al., 2002). Nonetheless, as to whether hypoxia produces an increase or a decrease of ROS in cells has been a matter of debate (see Michelakis et al., 2004; Hamanaka and Chandel, 2009), we directly addressed

this question by using glomus cells in slices transfected with a redox-sensitive fluorescent protein sensor (ro-GFP) genetically targeted to the mitochondrial intermembrane space (see Waypa et al., 2010)(Figure 7A). We were able to detect increases of ROS during exposure to hypoxia in cells from control mice, but this effect disappeared in CB slices from TH-NDUFS2 mice (Figures 7B and 7C). Interestingly, Ndufs4deficient cells, which are responsive to hypoxia (see Figures S3D and S3E), also showed increases of ROS in the intermembrane space upon exposure to low PO₂ (Figures 7B and 7C). Small increases of ROS during hypoxia observed in CB slices transfected with ro-GFP targeted to cytosol were also practically abolished in Ndufs2-deficient cells, although the redox sensor perfectly responded to the application of H₂O₂ (Figures S7E–S7H). In this preparation, we estimated mutant glomus cells to be oxidized with respect to controls (Figures 7D and 7E), which is in full agreement with the increase in input resistance and membrane depolarization observed in these cells (see Figures 3G, 6A, and 6B; Table S1). In addition to ROS, inhibition of MCI would be expected to produce an accumulation of NADH in mitochondria transferred to the cytosol by the malate/aspartate shuttle. We showed that the characteristic reversible increase in glomus cell NAD(P)H autofluorescence during exposure to hypoxia (Duchen and Biscoe, 1992; Buckler and Turner, 2013) was significantly reduced in Ndufs2-deficient cells (Figures 7F–7H). We also observed a significant increase in basal levels of NAD(P)H autofluorescence in Ndufs2null glomus cells with respect to controls (Figure 7I). Numerous reports have indicated that pyridine nucleotides can bind to voltage-gated K⁺ channel subunits and modulate their function (Tipparaju et al., 2005; Tamsett et al., 2009; Kilfoil et al., 2013). Loading glomus cells with NADH (150 μM in the whole-cell recording pipette), thereby mimicking the conditions that may exist in Ndufs2-deficient mice, markedly blunted the hypoxic modulation of the currents (Figures S7I and S7J). Thus, our data strongly suggest the existence in chemoreceptor cells of a MCI-dependent regulation of membrane K⁺ channels during hypoxia that is mediated by ROS with the possible co-participation of pyridine nucleotides.

Discussion

The results in this paper show that ablation of the Ndufs2 gene in mice leads to a loss of the reflex hyperventilatory response to hypoxia. They also demonstrate a selective abolition of responsiveness to hypoxia in Ndufs2-deficient CB and AM chemoreceptor cells. In sharp contrast,

the effects of direct membrane depolarization with high K^+ or the application of other stimuli such as hypercapnia and hypoglycemia, unrelated to hypoxia (see Peers and Buckler, 1995; Muñoz-Cabello et al., 2005; Gao et al., 2014), were unaltered. These observations indicate that acute O_2 sensing by peripheral chemoreceptors depends on MCI function and explain previous pharmacological data showing that rotenone selectively blocks sensitivity to hypoxia in CB and AM cells (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2003; García-Fernández et al., 2007a; Thompson et al., 2007). The correspondence of our findings with those reported in other cells of the homeostatic acute O_2 -sensing system (see Archer et al., 1993; Michelakis et al., 2002; Waypa hypoxia 0 glu CO_2 et al., 2001, 2013) is still to be determined. An unexpected observation in this study is that glomus cells, which are known to have a high O_2 consumption (Daly et al., 1954), can maintain normal ATP levels and ATP-consuming functions (e.g., ion gradients and exocytosis) without a functional MCI. We have shown that CB glomus cells contain unusually high levels of succinate, and in contrast to their resistance to MCI dysfunction, they are highly vulnerable to genetic disruption of succinate dehydrogenase (Díaz-Castro et al., 2012; Platero-Luengo et al., 2014). These data suggest a metabolic specialization in glomus cells due to a highly active anaplerotic metabolism supporting succinate-dependent ubiquinone reduction and oxidative phosphorylation. A less active anaplerotic metabolism and succinate-dependent mitochondrial function could explain why adult AM chromaffin cells are less sensitive to hypoxia than glomus cells. Taken together, the results argue against a decrease in mitochondrial ATP being the signal that modulates membrane ion channel activity during hypoxia (Wyatt and Buckler, 2004). Moreover, *Ndufs2*-deficient cells respiring with succinate exhibited optimal responsiveness to several stimuli but remained selectively insensitive to hypoxia.

The acute O_2 -sensing model that emerges from the data presented here implies that MCI in chemoreceptor cells can adopt two possible states characterized by either a low ROS-producing rate with NADH consumption (normoxia) or a high ROS-producing rate with NADH accumulation (hypoxia)(Figure 7J). To account for the physiological responses to hypoxia, transitions between these states must be fast and highly reversible. In addition, the transition to the hypoxic state must depend on specific metabolic properties making the cells more (e.g., glomus cells) or less (e.g., adult chromaffin cells) sensitive to hypoxia. Therefore, it could be that in glomus cells, with high succinate ($FADH_2$)dependent ubiquinone reduction (our data) and accelerated O_2 consumption (Daly et al., 1954), the slowdown of the ETC during hypoxia results in accumulation

of reduced quinone (QH₂), which in turn leads to a highly reduced state of MCI, increased production of ROS, and accumulation of NADH. Moreover, it is also possible that hypoxia induces even more drastic modifications in MCI function. MCI modulation in eukaryotic cells is poorly understood, but it is well established that, depending on the biochemical conditions, the enzyme can change its conformational state from an active to a deactive form (see Babot and Galkin, 2013). A biochemical characteristic that could favor the signaling role of MCI in acute O₂ sensing is the switching between the forward/reverse functions of the enzyme, an intriguing property of as yet unknown physiological significance (Votyakova and Reynolds, 2001; Liu et al., 2002; Lambert and Brand, 2004). In the reverse mode, QH₂ is oxidized to generate NADH and ROS at a rate that is >20 times greater than when the enzyme functions in the forward mode. Reverse MCI function is linked to the succinate-dependent, highly reduced state of the ubiquinone pool (Liu et al., 2002; Lambert and Brand, 2004, Pryde and Hirst, 2011). Therefore, it is plausible that the accumulation of QH₂ in glomus cells during hypoxia not only slows down MCI function but also is sufficient to induce reverse MCI function (red characters in Figure 7J). Rotenone blocks the forward and reverse functions of the enzyme and also induces a highly radical producing state due to a backlog of electrons in MCI (Votyakova and Reynolds, 2001; Lambert and Brand, 2004), thus explaining the efficiency of the drug in occluding responsiveness to hypoxia (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2003). In support of this model, *Ndufs4* deficient cells, in which the MCI quinone-binding site is unaltered and maintain about 40% of NADH-ubiquinone oxidoreductase activity (Kruse et al., 2008), retain sensitivity to hypoxia. This comprehensive model could explain the exquisite sensitivity of glomus cells to hypoxia and mitochondrial inhibitors and the particular efficacy of rotenone in blocking further actions of hypoxia. It is also compatible with the existence of other physiological mechanisms or pharmacological treatments leading to direct or indirect modulation of membrane K⁺ channels and thus modifying their sensitivity to changes in PO₂ (López-Barneo, 2003; Nurse et al., 2006; Evans et al., 2009; Prabhakar and Peers, 2014). Hypoxic chemotransduction might be facilitated by the localization of mitochondria near to the plasma membrane and by the small size of glomus cells, whose high membrane resistance converts minuscule changes of membrane current into a depolarization that is able to open voltage-gated Ca²⁺ channels. In summary, the association of responsiveness to acute hypoxia with MCI signaling unveils a fundamental process of broad biomedical significance that has remained elusive. Gaining a mechanistic insight into acute O₂ sensing not only enhances our understanding of arterial chemoreception but could also

boost knowledge on the pathogenesis of devastating disorders such as Parkinson's disease or Leigh's syndrome, which are caused by MCI dysfunction.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Animals

A floxed *Ndufs2* allele was engineered to generate TH-NDUFS2 and ESR-NDUFS2 mouse strains. Animals with the floxed *Ndufs4* allele were provided by Dr. A. Quintana. Transgenic and wildtype mice were housed and treated according to the animal care guidelines of the European Community Council (2010/63/EU). All procedures were approved by the Animal Research Committee at the University of Seville. Unless otherwise specified, 2-month-old TH-NDUFS2 mice were used. TMX treatment of ESR-NDUFS2 animals was also started at this age. Mice were anesthetized with thiopental 90–120 mg/kg before sacrificing and tissue dissection. Unless otherwise noted, dissected tissues were fast-frozen with liquid N₂ and stored at -80°C for further analysis.

Plethysmography

To determine the pulmonary function, awake, unrestricted mice were placed inside the plethysmography chambers (EMKA Technologies) as previously described (Maci'as et al., 2014). Chambers were constantly perfused with air containing either 21% O₂ (normoxia), 10% O₂ (hypoxia), or 5% CO₂ (hypercapnia). Experimental protocol consisted of either two cycles of normoxia-hypoxia-normoxia or one cycle of normoxia-hypoxia-normoxia-hypercapnia-normoxia with at least 5 min of stabilized O₂ or CO₂ levels in each condition. O₂ and CO₂ tensions and breathing frequency were continuously monitored and recorded in each experiment.

Immunohistochemical Studies and ATP and Succinate Measurements

For detection of TH in tissue sections and estimation of cell number and volume of CB, AM, and SCG, we used standard procedures. ATP content in these same tissues was measured as described previously (Díaz-Castro et al., 2012). Succinate measurement in rat tissues was done following manufacturer's instruction. Specific details of these procedures are given in the Supplemental Information.

Electron Microscopy

Electron microscopy of CBs was performed as previously described (Maci'as et al., 2014). Images were obtained using a transmission EM (Zeiss Libra 120). The number of dense core vesicles and mitochondrial density was estimated in cell sections using ImageJ software. Mitochondrial density was calculated as percentage of mitochondrial area/cytoplasm area.

RealTime Quantitative PCR, Western Blot Analysis, and Blue Native Polyacrylamide Gel Electrophoresis

Quantitative PCR analyses were done following standard procedures. Protein levels were analyzed in kidney and AM. Tissues were homogenized in RIPA buffer supplemented with protease inhibitor cocktail and protein phosphatase inhibitor cocktail (Sigma) to obtain whole-cell or subcellular protein extracts. Further details on these methodologies and specific antibodies used are given in the Supplemental Information. To study mitochondrial complex formation, blue native polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (BNPAGE) was performed as described previously (Wittig et al., 2006). Mitochondria were isolated the same way as to measure mitochondrial complex activities (Díaz-Castro et al., 2012). Mitochondrial proteins (125 mg) were solubilized with digitonin (6 g per g of mitochondria) and separated on 3%–13%acrylamide gradient gels. After electrophoresis, the gels were processed either for Coomassie staining or for western blotting. For Coomassie staining, gels were submerged in a staining solution (0.25% Coomassie blue R250, 40% methanol, and 10% acetic acid) for 2 hr before destaining and photographing.

Mitochondrial Complex Activities and Oxygen Consumption Mitochondria were isolated from mouse kidneys, and maximum enzymatic activities of MCI and MCII were measured with a spectrophotometer as previously described (Díaz-Castro et al., 2012). MCI activity in the SCG was estimated using an enzyme activity dipstick assay; MCI and MCII activities were also determined by monitoring the rate of oxygen consumption in the presence of the complex-specific substrates with a Clark oxygen electrode. Details of these methodologies are given in the Supplemental Information.

Amperometric Recording of Single Cell Catecholamine Secretion in Tissue Slices

Exocytotic catecholamine secretion from cells in CB and AM slices was performed as described in previous papers from our laboratory (Piruat et al., 2004; Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2006). Specific details are given in the Supplemental Information.

Cell Dispersion, Patch Clamp, and Microfluorimetric Recordings Enzymatic dispersion of mouse CB cells, electrophysiological recordings, and microfluorimetric measurements of cytosolic Ca²⁺ and NAD(P)H were performed following the methods described in previous publications from our laboratory (Ureña et al., 1994; Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2010). To measure mitochondria ROS production in CB slices, we used a ro-GFP sensor targeted to either the cytosol or the mitochondrial intermembrane space as previously described (see Waypa et al., 2010). Details of these methodologies are given in the Supplemental Information.

Statistical Analysis

Unless otherwise specified, data were presented as mean \pm SEM with the number (n) of experiments indicated. Normality was tested with the Shapiro-Wilk test. When necessary, a log transformation was performed to normalize the distribution prior to parametric analyses. Data from two groups were analyzed with either t test or paired t test. Data with multiple groups were analyzed with ANOVA or RM ANOVA followed by post hoc Tukey's test. For data without normal distribution or equal variance, nonparametric tests (Mann-Whitney rank sum test, ANOVA on ranks, or RM ANOVA on ranks followed by post hoc Tukey's test) were performed. Raw data were used for statistical analysis to determine the potential difference among groups in the physiological studies (Figures 3C, 3D, 6D–6G, S2H, and S2J). In order to better visualize these results, normalized data (% to normoxia Nx) were presented in the figures. A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Supplemental Information includes seven figures, one table, and Supplemental Experimental Procedures and can be found with this article online at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2015.09.004>.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

M.C.F.A., L.G., P.G.R., C.O.P., I.A.M., P.G.F., A.G.P., A.P., and P.O.S. performed experiments; M.C.F.A., L.G., P.G.R., A.P., P.O.S., and J.L.B. designed the study and prepared a draft of the manuscript. J.L.B. coordinated the project and the writing of the paper.

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Figure legends

Ventilatory response to hypoxia and hypercapnia

Carotid body structure

Carotid body metabolic status

Figure 1. Absence of HVR in TH-NDUFS2 Mice, with Preservation of CB Cell Properties (A and B) Plethysmograph recordings and changes in breathing frequency during exposure to hypoxia (10% O₂) in TH-NDUFS2 mice (n = 9) compared to their control (n = 11) littermates. (C and D) Changes in breathing frequency during exposure to hypoxia (10% O₂) or hypercapnia (5% CO₂) in TH-NDUFS2 mice (n = 4) compared to their control (n = 3) littermates. (E) Tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) immunostaining of CBs of control and TH-NDUFS2 mice. Scale bars: 50 μm. (F and G) Quantification of total CB volume (F) and TH⁺ cell number (G) of control (blue, n = 5) and TH-NDUFS2 (light brown, n = 4) mice. (H) Electron micrographs of CB sections showing the increase of mitochondria (arrowheads) and decrease of dense core vesicles (insets) in Ndufs2-deficient cells. Scale bars: 2 μm. (I and J) Quantification of number of vesicles per cell section (n = 13 and 27 for control and TH-NDUFS2 mice, respectively; 3 mice per group) and mitochondria (percentage of mitochondrial area/cytoplasm area) (n = 3 mice). (K) Ndufs2 mRNA levels in CBs of control and TH-NDUFS2 heterozygous and homozygous mice (n = 3–5/group). Levels of succinate dehydrogenase subunit D (Sdhb) mRNA were measured for comparison. (L) ATP content in CBs of control and TH-NDUFS2 heterozygous and homozygous mice (n = 10–12/group). (M) Succinate content in brain, CB, and AM (n = 3 to 4) from wildtype adult rats. All quantitative data are expressed as mean ± SEM. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01.

Figure 2. Selective Loss of Glomus Cell Responsiveness to Hypoxia in TH-NDUFS2 Mice

- (A) Schematic drawing of quantal dopamine release from a glomus cell recorded with the amperometric technique.
- (B) Quantal dopamine secretion from glomus cells in CB slices of wildtype (control) and TH-NDUFS2 mice in response to depolarization with 40 mM KCl.
- (C) (Left) Average secretion rate (pC/min) in response to 40 mM KCl measured in glomus cells from wildtype (blue, n = 36 cells, 17 mice) and TH-NDUFS2 (light brown, n = 21 cells, 13 mice) animals. (Right) Average mean vesicle content calculated as secretion rate (femtoC/min)/frequency of spikes (spikes/min). Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM.
- (D and E) Catecholamine release from glomus cells in CB slices from wildtype (control, [D]) and TH-NDUFS2 (E) mice exposed to low PO₂ (10 mmHg), 20% CO₂, and 0 mM glucose. Cumulative secretion signals are shown below each trace (red). The vertical discontinuous lines indicate resetting of the integrator.
- (F) Percentage of cells with a secretory response to hypoxia, 0 mM glucose, and hypercapnia (20%CO₂) in wildtype (n = 34/17, 15/9, and 7/3 slices/mice, respectively) and TH-NDUFS2 (n = 21/11, 19/8, and 14/7 slices/mice, respectively) animals.
- (G) Scatter plot of dopamine secretion measured in hypoxia-responding cells from control (n = 28) and TH-NDUFS2 (n = 3) mice.

Membrane currents in control and Ndufs2-deficient cells

Figure 3. Loss of K⁺ Channel Modulation by Hypoxia in Glomus Cells from TH-NDUFS2 Mice

(A) (Top) Voltage ramp protocol applied to dispersed glomus cells studied with the perforated-patch technique. Currents were recorded from control (middle) and Ndufs2-deficient (bottom) cells for normoxia (Nx, PO₂ 145 mm Hg, red), hypoxia (Hx, PO₂ 10 mmHg, blue), and recovery in normoxia (R, gray) conditions. (B) (Top) Voltage ramp protocol applied to patch-clamped cells.

Holding currents recorded from control and Ndufs2-deficient glomus cells in normoxia, hypoxia, and recovery conditions. Recordings are the same as in (A). (C and D) Normalized outward K⁺ current amplitude (at -10 mV) and values of input resistance in glomus cells from control (n = 19/5 cells/mice) and TH-NDUFS2 (n = 21/5 cells/mice) animals in normoxia (Nx), hypoxia (Hx), and recovery (R) conditions. In this and the following panels, discontinuous lines indicate 100% values used for normalization. (E and F) Voltage-dependent K⁺ (E) and holding (F) currents recorded in glomus cells from control (blue) and TH-NDUFS2 (light brown) mice. G) Values of input resistance (left) and outward current amplitude (right) at -10 mV in control (n = 27) and Ndufs2-deficient (n = 24) glomus cells (n = 7 mice per group). Data in (C), (D), and (G) are expressed as mean ± SEM. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01.

Figure 4. Loss of Responsiveness to Hypoxia of AM Chromaffin Cells from TH-NDUFS2 Mice

A and B) TH immunostaining (A) and volume quantification (mean \pm SEM) (B) of AM in control (blue, $n = 6$) and TH-NDUFS2 (light brown, $n = 6$) mice. Scale bars: 500 μm . (C) ATP content (mean \pm SEM) in the AM of control and TH-NDUFS2 heterozygous and homozygous mice ($n = 11/\text{group}$). (D) *Ndufs2* and *Sdhd* (succinate dehydrogenase subunit D) mRNA levels (mean \pm SEM) in the AM of control and TH-NDUFS2 heterozygous and homozygous mice ($n = 4$ to $5/\text{group}$). The inset at the top represents a western blot demonstrating the decreased *Ndufs2* protein level in TH-NDUFS2 heterozygous and homozygous mice in comparison to control littermates.

(E and F) Amperometric signals showing catecholamine released from chromaffin cells in AM slices from wildtype (control) and TH-NDUFS2 mice. Cumulative secretion signal (pC) resulting from the time integral of the amperometric recording (red). The vertical discontinuous lines indicate resetting of the integrator. hypercapnia (20% CO₂) in control (blue, n = 8/3 slices/mice) and TH-NDUFS2 (light brown; n = 6/3 slices/mice) animals. None of the cells tested responded to hypoxia. (H) Average secretion rate (mean ± SEM) measured in basal conditions and during exposure to hypoxia and hypercapnia in cells from wildtype (blue, n = 8, 6, and 6 slices, respectively) and TH-NDUFS2 (light brown, n = 6 slices) mice (n = 3 per group). (I) Secretion rate (mean ± SEM) during exposure to 20 mM KCl in cells from wildtype (blue, n = 8 slices) and TH-NDUFS2 (light brown, n = 5 slices) mice (n = 3 per group). *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01.

Figure 5. Mitochondrial Complex I Dysfunction and Abolition of O₂ Sensing in Ndufs2-deficient Glomus Cells

(A) (Left) Representative blue native gel demonstrating lack of mitochondrial complex I (MCI) assembly in kidney cells from ESR-NDUFS2 mice. (Right top) Crystal structure of MCI from *Thermus thermophiles*. Analyzed proteins are highlighted in red. (Right middle) Blue native gels

followed by western blot analysis demonstrating lack of MCI assembly compared to other mitochondrial complexes in kidney cells from ESR-NDUFS2 mice. For comparison proteins from MCII (Sdhb), MCIII (Uqcrrf1), and MCIV (mtCo1) were also analyzed. (Right bottom) Representative western blots of proteins involved in the mitochondrial ETC from kidney whole-cell extracts of control and ESR-NDUFS2 mice. SC, supercomplex; I to V, mitochondrial complex I to V; subI, subcomplex of MCI. (B and C) MCI and MCII activities (mean \pm SEM) measured in kidney mitochondria from control and ESR-NDUFS2 heterozygous and homozygous mice (n = 4–8/group). (D–F) O₂ consumption specific to MCI (malate and pyruvate) and MCII (Suc: succinate) measured in mitochondria from kidney cells of control and ESR-NDUFS2 mice (n = 3–5/group) (mean \pm SEM). Rot: rotenone. Ant: antimycin A. (G and H) Cytosolic [Ca²⁺] changes elicited by hypoxia, hypercapnia, and high K⁺ in dispersed glomus cells from control and TH-NDUFS2 mice, incubated in the presence of 4 mM succinate. (I) Percentage of control (blue, n = 74, 13, and 15 from six mice, respectively) and Ndufs2-deficient (light brown, n = 29, 19, and 14 from five mice, respectively) cells exhibiting an increase in cytosolic [Ca²⁺] in response to hypoxia, 0 mM glucose, or hypercapnia (20% CO₂). *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01.

Figure 6. Effects of Intracellular Redox Agents on O₂-sensitive K⁺ Currents in Normal and Ndufs2-deficient Glomus Cells

(A) (Left) Increase in the holding current in Ndufs2-deficient glomus cells following the intracellular application of N-acetylLcysteine (NAC) (25 mM). (Right) Average input resistance changes (inversely proportional to the holding current) in Ndufs2-deficient cells dialyzed with NAC (<50 mM, n = 8, from three mice per group). (B) (Left) Decrease in the holding current

in control glomus cells following intracellular application of H₂O₂ (15 mM). (Right) Input resistance changes (mean \pm SEM) measured in wildtype glomus cells dialyzed with NAC (25 mM, n = 10) or H₂O₂ (15–50 mM, n = 11). Control (n = 15) (n = 6 mice). (C) Representative traces of currents recorded in Ndufs2-deficient (top) and control (bottom) glomus cells with NAC (25 mM) or H₂O₂ (15 mM) in the patchpipette. (D and E) Input resistance changes (mean \pm SEM) and peak outward membrane currents in Ndufs2-deficient glomus cells with (n = 7 from 5 mice) and without (n = 5 from 5 mice) intracellular application of NAC (25 mM) under normoxia (Nx), hypoxia (Hx), and recovery (R) conditions. In this and the following panels, discontinuous lines indicate 100% values used for normalization. (F and G) Input resistance changes and peak outward membrane currents (mean \pm SEM) in control glomus cells with (n = 8 and 7, respectively) and without (n = 21) intracellular application of H₂O₂ (15 mM) or NAC (25–50 mM) for normoxia (Nx), hypoxia (Hx), and recovery (R) conditions. Data from six mice. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01.

Figure 7. Mitochondrial Complex I Signaling and Hypoxia Responsiveness of Glomus Cells

(A) Fluorescence images of CB slices transfected with a ROS-sensitive probe (ro-GFP) targeted to the mitochondrial intermembrane space (Ims) and overlap of ro-GFP and MitoTracker (a mitochondrial marker) fluorescence. Scale bars: 10 mm. (B and C) Changes in ROS in the intermembrane space during exposure of control and Ndufs2 or Ndufs4-deficient glomus cells to hypoxia. Numbers of cells recorded are control (blue bar, n = 29/4 cells/mice), TH-NDUFS2 (light

brown, n = 31/5 cells/mice), and TH-NDUFS4 (green, n = 25/4, cells/mice). (D) Change of ROS in glomus cells from slices transfected with a ro-GFP probe targeted to the cytosol. Signal calibration with DTT (1 mM, dithiothreitol) and H₂O₂ (0.1 mM). (E) Comparison of the basal level of oxidation estimated in control (n = 26) and Ndufs2-deficient (n = 49) glomus cells (four mice per group) (mean ± SEM). (F) Changes in NAD(P)H autofluorescence (arbitrary units) during exposure of glomus cells from control and TH-NDUFS2 mice to hypoxia. (G) Percentage of control (n = 69 from nine mice) and Ndufs2-deficient (n = 83 from seven mice) cells with changes in NAD(P)H autofluorescence in response to hypoxia. (H) Intensity of the hypoxia-induced NAD(P)H autofluorescence signal (mean ± SEM) in hypoxia-responding glomus cells from control (blue, n = 57) and TH-NDUFS2 (light brown, n = 6) mice. (I) Basal level of NAD(P)H autofluorescence signal (mean ± SEM) in control (n = 25 from 12 mice) and Ndufs2-deficient (n = 17 from six mice) glomus cells. (J) Model of acute O₂ sensing in chemoreceptor cells. Reduced quinone (QH₂). *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01.

Supplemental Information

Oxygen Sensing by Arterial Chemoreceptors Depends on Mitochondrial Complex I Signaling

M. Carmen Fernández-Agüera, Lin Gao, Patricia González-Rodríguez, C. Oscar Pintado, Ignacio Arias-Mayenco, Paula García-Flores, Antonio García-Pergañeda, Alberto Pascual, Patricia Ortega-Sáenz, and José López-Barneo

Supplemental Information

This file contains:

Supplemental Data (Figures S1 to S7, Table S1)

Supplemental Experimental Procedures

Supplemental References

TH-NDUFS2 mouse

Figure S1

Figure S1. Related to Figure 1. Generation and Characterization of the TH-NDUFS2 Mouse.

(A) Scheme illustrating the strategy followed to generate *Ndufs2* floxed and excised alleles. H, HpaI. B, BmtI. E1-3, exons 1-3. Probe and genotyping primers are indicated. Arrows indicate the location of PCR primers. FRT: flipase (FLP) recombinase target. (B) Genotyping of *Ndufs2*^{+/+} (+/+) and *Ndufs2*^{F/+} (F/+) mice by southern blot analysis using HpaI-BmtI digested DNA from mouse brain hybridized with the probe indicated in (A). (C) Genotyping of *Ndufs2*^{+/+} (+/+), *Ndufs2*^{F/+} (F/+), *Ndufs2*^{F/F} (F/F), and *Ndufs2*^{+/-} (+/-) mice by PCR. (D) Representative pictures of control and TH-NDUFS2 mice (P60). (E) Growth curves of control and TH-NDUFS2 heterozygous and homozygous mice (male: n=8-23/group/time point; female: n=5-20/group/time point). Data are expressed as mean±SEM. (F) Mitochondrial complex I (MCI) activity (mean±SEM) in the superior cervical ganglion (SCG) of control and TH-NDUFS2 mice (n=3 replicates from 4 mice each) determined using MCI activity dipstick assay. (G) Average secretion rate (in picocoulombs, (pC)/min) in response to low PO₂ (~10 mmHg, n=27), 0 mM glucose (n=11), and 20% CO₂ (n=5) in carotid body slices from wild-type mice (n=17, 9, 3, respectively) recorded with the amperometric technique (mean±SEM). *p<0.05, **p<0.01.

Whole-cell patch clamp

Perforated patch clamp

Figure S2

Figure S2. Related to Figures 2 and 3. Voltage-Dependent Ionic Currents and Loss of Voltage-Gated K⁺ Channel Modulation by Hypoxia in Glomus Cells from Control and TH-NDUFS2 Mice.

(A,B) Representative recordings of potassium currents in whole-cell patch clamped dispersed glomus cells from control and TH-NDUFS2 mice. Depolarizing (50 ms) voltage steps between -30 and +50 mV were applied from a holding potential of -70 mV. (C) Average peak potassium current density (pA/pF) (mean±SEM) versus voltage (membrane potential, V_m) relationship obtained from control (blue, n= 25) and Ndufs2-deficient (light brown, n= 19) glomus cells (n= 5 mice/group). (D,E) Representative macroscopic calcium and sodium currents recorded in glomus cells from control and TH-NDUFS2 mice during a depolarization to +10 mV from a holding potential of -70 mV. Although no qualitative differences were seen, the number of cells with a fast inward Na⁺ current was higher in the case of Ndufs2-deficient glomus cells. (F) Average peak calcium current density (pA/pF) (mean±SEM) versus voltage (membrane potential, V_m) relationship obtained from control (blue, n= 25) and Ndufs2-deficient (light brown, n=19) glomus cells (n= 7 mice/group). The decrease of average peak Ca²⁺ current amplitude was not statistically significant. (G,H) Macroscopic potassium currents recorded in glomus cells (perforated-patch configuration) from control and TH-NDUFS2 mice during step depolarizations to -10 mV. Note that the hypoxia-induced decrease in K⁺ current amplitude was abolished in TH-NDUFS2 glomus cells. The quantitative plot (mean±SEM) was obtained from control (n=13) and Ndufs2-deficient (n=10) cells (4 mice/group). Normoxia (Nx, PO₂ ~145 mm Hg), hypoxia (Hx, PO₂ ~10 mmHg) and recovery (R, normoxia after hypoxic treatment). In this and the other panel discontinuous lines indicate 100% values used for normalization. (I,J) Hypercapnia-induced decrease in potassium currents recorded in glomus cells from control and TH-NDUFS2 mice. The quantitative plot (mean±SEM) was obtained from control (n= 10) and Ndufs2-deficient (n=9) cells (4 mice/group). **p<0.01.

TH-NDUFS4 mouse

Figure S3

Figure S3. Related to Figures 1 and 2. Responsiveness of *Ndufs4*-Deficient Glomus Cells to Hypoxia.

(A,B) *Ndufs4* deletion in peripheral catecholaminergic tissues of TH-NDUFS4 mice. *Ndufs4* and *Sdhd* mRNA levels in the adrenal medulla (AM) and superior cervical ganglion (SCG) of control (+/+) and TH-NDUFS4 heterozygous (+/-) or homozygous (-/-) animals (n=4-7/group). (C) For comparison, same analysis of *Ndufs2* allele deletion in SCG is shown for TH-NDUFS2 mice (n= 4-5/group). Data on AM are shown in Fig. 4D. (D) Amperometric recordings on carotid body slices obtained from TH-NDUFS4 mice. Note the normal responses of glomus cells to hypoxia and hypoglycemia. Cumulative secretion signals are shown below each trace (red). The vertical discontinuous line indicates resetting of the integrator. (E) Catecholamine secretion values (in fC/min) reached during exposure to hypoxia in comparison with the levels in normoxia (basal) (n=7 slices from 4 mice). Data in A, B, C and E are expressed as (mean±SEM). *p<0.05, **p<0.01.

Hypoxic ventilatory response

Carotid body

Secretory activity in carotid body slices

Figure S4

Figure S4. Related to Figures 2 and 4. Generation and Characterization of the ESR-NDUFS2 Mouse.

(A-C) Representative plethysmograph recordings showing changes in breathing frequency during two cycles of normoxia-hypoxia-normoxia in ESR-NDUFS2 mice compared to their control littermates. Average breathing frequencies (mean±SEM) during normoxia (~21% O₂) and hypoxia (10% O₂) in control (n=10) and ESR-NDUFS2 (n=10) mice. (D) Immunostaining of tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) in carotid bodies (CBs). Scale bars: 50 μm. (E) Quantification (mean±SEM) of CB volume and TH+ cell number in control (blue, n=4) and ESR-NDUFS2 (light brown, n=5) mice. (F) *Ndufs2* and *Sdhd* mRNA levels (mean±SEM) in the CB of control and ESR-NDUFS2 heterozygous and homozygous mice (n=4-5 replicates/group from 3-4 mice each). (G,H) Amperometric and cumulative dopamine secretion signals recorded from glomus cells in CB slices of control and ESR-NDUFS2 mice exposed to hypoxia (PO₂, ~10 mmHg) and hypercapnia (20% CO₂). The discontinuous vertical line indicates resetting of the integrator. (I) Dopamine release (pC/min) (mean±SEM) from control (n=11/4 slices/mice) and *Ndufs2*-deficient (n=7/4 slices/mice) glomus cells in response to depolarization with 40 mM KCl. (J) Percentage of glomus cells presenting a secretory response to hypoxia, 0 mM glucose and hypercapnia in control (n=18, 10, and 8, respectively from 7 mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (n=7, 7, and 11, respectively from 4 mice) animals. (K) Scattered diagram of dopamine release from hypoxia-responsive cells in control (n=11) and ESR-NDUFS2 (n=2) mice. *p<0.05, **p<0.01.

Adrenal medulla

Secretory activity in adrenal chromaffin cells

Figure S5

Figure S5. Related to Figure 4. Secretory Responses to Hypoxia, Hypercapnia and High K⁺ of Adrenal Chromaffin Cells.

(A,B) Immunostaining of tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) in the adrenal medulla (AM) and quantification (mean±SEM) of AM volume in control (blue, n=4) and ESR-NDUFS2 (light brown, n=5) mice. Scale bars: 500 μm. (C) *Ndufs2* and *Sdhd* mRNA levels (mean±SEM) in the AM of control and ESR-NDUFS2 heterozygous and homozygous mice (n=4-5/group). (D,E) Amperometric signal showing catecholamine release from chromaffin cells in AM slices from control and ESR-NDUFS2 mice. Cumulative secretion signal (in picocoulombs, pC), obtained from the time integral of the amperometric recording (red). The vertical discontinuous lines indicate resetting of the integrator. (F) Percentage of cells responding to hypoxia and hypercapnia (20%CO₂) in control (blue, n= 6 slices from 3 mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (light brown; n=7 slices from 3 mice) animals. None of the *Ndufs2*-deficient cells tested responded to hypoxia. (G) Average secretion rate (mean±SEM) measured in basal conditions and during exposure to hypoxia and hypercapnia in control (blue, n=6 slices from 3 mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (light brown, n=7 slices from 3 mice) animals. (H) Average secretion rate (mean±SEM) measured during exposure to 20 mM KCl in control (blue, n= 6 slices from 3 mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (light brown, n=7 slices from 3 mice) animals.

Figure S6

Figure S6. Related to Figure 5. Mitochondrial Function in ESR-NDUFS2 Mice.

(A) (Left) *Ndufs2* mRNA levels (mean±SEM) in kidney cells of control and ESR-NDUFS2 heterozygous and homozygous mice (n=4/group). (Right) Representative western blot analysis and quantification (mean±SEM) demonstrating the decreased *Ndufs2* protein level in ESR-NDUFS2 mice compared to their control littermates (n=4-5 per group). (B) Average levels (mean±SEM) of complex I (*Ndufs2*, *Ndufs1*, *Ndufv2*, mt-*Nd1*), complex II (*Sdha*, *Sdhb*), complex III (*Uqcrcfs1*) and complex IV (mt-*Co1*) proteins estimated by western blot (n=3-4/group). (C,D) Representative western blot analysis and quantification (mean±SEM) (n=4/group) of subcellular mitochondrial complex I proteins in the kidney of the ESR-NDUFS2 mice. Cytosolic (Cyto) and mitochondrial (Mito) fractions were validated by the expression of α -tubulin and *Vdac*, respectively. (*Ndufs2*, *Ndufs1*, *Ndufv2*: nuclear coded proteins; mt-*Nd1*: mitochondrial encoded protein). Note that only a slight accumulation of nuclear encoded proteins (*Ndufs1* and *Ndufv2*) was observed in the cytosolic fraction in *Ndufs2* KO mice. Therefore, the data indicate that the lack of *Ndufs2* protein in the *Ndufs2* KO mice leads to the degradation of non-assembled MCI proteins. *p<0.05, **p<0.01.

Figure S7

Figure S7. Related to Figures 6 and 7. Mitochondrial Complex I Signaling and Hypoxia Responsiveness of Glomus Cells.

(A) Input resistance changes (mean±SEM) in control glomus cells with (n=7) and without (n=11) intracellular application of the thiol oxidizing agent diamide (50-60 μ M). (B) (Top) Voltage ramp protocol applied to dispersed glomus cells studied with the perforated-patch technique. Representative traces of O₂-sensitive K⁺ currents recorded in control glomus cells with diamide in the patch pipette under normoxia (Nx), hypoxia (Hx), and recovery (R) conditions. (C,D) Values (mean±SEM) of input resistance and normalized outward K⁺ current amplitude (at -10 mV) in glomus cells with (n=7) and without (n=11) intracellular application of diamide under normoxia, hypoxia, and recovery conditions. Discontinuous lines indicate 100% values used for normalization. (E,F) Changes in levels of cytosolic ROS during exposure of control (E) and Ndufs2-deficient (F) glomus cells to hypoxia. Glomus cells from slices were transfected with a roGFP probe targeted to the cytosol. (G) Response of the roGFP probe to application of H₂O₂ (20 μ M). (H) Percentage of cells responding to hypoxia and H₂O₂. Numbers of cells are: control (blue: hypoxia, n=73; H₂O₂, n=55), TH-NDUFS2 (light brown, hypoxia, n=71; H₂O₂, n=43) (4 mice/group). (I) Whole-cell voltage-dependent potassium currents recorded from patch-clamped glomus cells with (NADH) and without (control) NADH (150 μ M) added to the internal solution. (J) Quantitative analysis (mean±SEM) of the effect of NADH on hypoxic regulation of voltage-dependent K⁺ currents elicited by depolarization to the indicated membrane potentials (mV). Control (n=11); with internal NADH (n= 8) (n=4 mice). *p<0.05, **p<0.01.

Table S1. Related to Figures 3 and 6. Electrophysiological parameters of control and Ndufs2-deficient glomus cells

	CONTROL (Whole-cell)	TH-NDUFS2 (Whole-cell)	CONTROL (Amphotericin)	TH-NDUFS2 (Amphotericin)
Cell Capacitance (pF)	3.46 ± 0.17 (25)	3.75 ± 0.25 (25)	-	-
Input Resistance (GOhm)	1.35 ± 0.15 (25)	4.41 ± 0.61** (26)	2.30 ± 0.32 (27)	10.80 ± 2.11** (24)
Membrane Potential (mV)	-	-	-56.50 ± 2.95 (14)	-40.91 ± 2.28* (10)
I _{Na} holding (pA)	-	-	14.25 ± 4.06 (12)	12.52 ± 1.97 (7)
Reversal Potential (mV)	-	-	-66.40 ± 2.66 (21)	-49.70 ± 3.41** (24)

Data are given as mean ± standard error and the number of cells between parentheses.
 Statistical significance with respect to values in control animals: *p<0.05; **p<0.01.

Table S1

SUPPLEMENTAL EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Generation of TH-NDUFS2 and ESR-NDUFS2 Mice Strains and Animal Treatments

To obtain the genetically modified animal models used in this study a floxed allele (*Ndufs2^{flox-frt}*) was engineered in which exon 2 of the *Ndufs2* gene was flanked by two LoxP sites and a *neo* resistance marker flanked by two FLP recombinase target (FRT) sites was added right after the second LoxP site (Fig. S1A). This construct was targeted to the *Ndufs2* genomic locus by homologous recombination in 129Sv-derived R1 ES cells. Proper targeting was tested by southern blotting, in which genomic DNA was digested with restriction enzymes (HpaI and BmtI) and hybridized against a 5' probe (Fig. S1A). ES cell clones carrying the *Ndufs2^{flox-frt}* allele were used for blastocyst injection and chimera generation. Heterozygous animals carrying the *Ndufs2^{flox-frt}* allele, which was also confirmed by southern blot analysis (Fig. S1B), were bred with transgenic mice expressing FLP recombinase (Jackson Laboratory, Rodríguez et al., 2000) to remove the *neo* resistance marker in order to prevent its potential secondary effect. The resulting mice carrying *Ndufs2^{flox}* allele were subsequently mated with mice expressing either Th-IRES-Cre (Lindeberg et al., 2004) or tamoxifen-inducible Cre recombinase (Hayashi and McMahon, 2002) transgenes to generate the experimental mouse strains, TH-NDUFS2 and ESR-NDUFS2, respectively. TH-NDUFS4 mice were generated by crossing animals containing a floxed *Ndufs4* allele (Kruse et al., 2008) with our Th-IRES-Cre. All strains were further propagated and used for experiments on a mixed genetic background (129SvJ:C57BL/6). Adult ESR-NDUFS2 mice (~2 month old) were treated with tamoxifen-containing diet (TAM400/CreER, 400mg tamoxifen citrate/kg, Harlan Laboratories) for a month followed by 3-4 weeks of normal diet before experiments (Fig. S3A). The genotype of each mouse was determined by PCR using different primers to detect each allele (*Ndufs2⁺* and *Ndufs2^{flox}*, Fx51 5'-ATAAGAGTGGATAGGATGTTT-3' and Fx31 5'-CATTCTCCCTTCCCGTC-3'; *Ndufs2⁻*, Fx51 and FRT1 5'-AGTGGCAGAACAATAGAGTGATCCAGGG-3'). The genotype of NDUFS4 mouse was determined by PCR using the following primers: 1060, 5'-AGCCTGTTCTCATACTCGG-3'; 1061, 5'-GTCCTCTATGAGGGTACAGAG-3'; 1139, 5'-GGTGCATACTTATACTACTAGTAG-3'.

Immunohistochemistry

Carotid bifurcations and adrenal glands were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (Sigma) in PBS for 2 hours, cryoprotected overnight with 30% sucrose in PBS and embedded in OCT (Tissue-Tek). Tissue sections of 10 μm , which were cut with cryostat, were incubated with tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) antibody (Novus Biological) followed by the fluorescent secondary antibody Alexa568 (Invitrogen). Nuclei were detected by 4',6'-diamidino-2-phenylindole staining. Photographs of immunostained tissues were analyzed with ImageJ software to quantify the size of SCG, CB, and AM and the number of TH-positive cells in the CB. To estimate the volume of the AM in TH-NDUFS2 mice, adrenal glands were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS and paraffin-embedded. Sections with a thickness of 10 μm were cut with microtome (Leica). Immunoreactivity against TH antibody was detected with DAB using Envision⁺ System-HRP (Dako Cytomation).

ATP and Succinate Measurements

ATP content was measured as described previously (Díaz-Castro et al 2012). In brief, tissues were homogenized in homogenization solution (100mM Tris, 4 mM EDTA, pH7.75), boiled for 3 min followed by centrifugation for 1 min at 1000g. The concentration of ATP in the supernatants was determined using the ATP Bioluminescence Assay CLS II kit (Roche Applied Science) following the manufacturer's instructions and normalized with the absorbance at 260 nm. Succinate content in the CBs, AMs and brain from wild-type rats (2 months old) was measured using the succinate (succinic acid) colorimetric assay kit (BioVision) following the manufacturer's instructions. The amount was normalized with the protein content, which was determined using the Bio-Rad protein assay (BioRad), and presented as nmol/ μg protein.

Real-Time Quantitative PCR

Total RNAs were isolated either with Trizol reagent (Life technologies) from kidney or RNeasy micro kit (Qiagen) from CB, SCG, and AM, as previously described (Gao et al., 2013). Due to the small tissue size, each CB replicate was pooled from ≥ 3 mice to obtain enough amount of RNA. In addition, CB cRNA was amplified using Ambion WT expression kit (Life technologies). Five hundred or less ng of total RNA (or amplified cRNA in the case of CB) was copied to cDNA using QuantiTect Reverse

Transcription Kit (Qiagen) in a final volume of 20 μ l. Real-time quantitative PCR reactions were performed in a 7500 Fast Real Time PCR System (Life Technologies). PCR reactions were performed in duplicates in a total volume of 20 μ l containing 1-2.5 μ l of cDNA solution and 1 μ l of Taqman probe of the specific gene (Life Technologies). *Gapdh* was also estimated in each sample to normalize the amount of total RNA (or cRNA) input in order to perform relative quantifications.

Western Blot Analysis

To determine protein levels, kidney, SCG, and AM were homogenized in RIPA buffer supplemented with protease inhibitor cocktail and protein phosphatase inhibitor cocktail (Sigma) to obtain whole cell protein extracts, as previously described (Gao et al., 2011). Homogenates were incubated on ice for 15 min, followed by centrifugation at 13,200 rpm for 10 min. The supernatants were utilized to estimate the amount of mitochondrial proteins by western blot analysis. Fifty (kidney) or 10 (SCG, AM) μ g of protein, as determined with the Bradford method (BioRad Protein Assay, BioRad), were run on a 10% SDS-PAGE gel and transferred to PVDF membranes. These membranes were incubated first with primary antibodies then with the horseradish peroxidase-conjugated secondary antibodies. The primary antibodies were: β -actin, mt-Co1, mt-Nd1, Ndufs1, Ndufs2, Ndufv2, Sdha, Sdhb, Uqcrcfs1 (Abcam) and Rpl26 (Sigma). Blots were revealed with either LuminataTM Crescendo Western HRP Substrate (Millipore) or ClarityTM Western ECL substrate (BioRad) and scanned with a luminescent image analyzer (ImageQuant LAS 4000mini, GE Healthcare). The signal intensity was quantified using the ImageQuant TL software (GE Healthcare). Protein levels of β -actin or Rpl26 were used to normalize the amount of total protein input in order to perform relative quantifications.

To further investigate the homeostasis of mitochondrial complex I (MCI) proteins in *Ndufs2*-deficient cells, cytosolic and mitochondrial fractions were obtained from the kidney of ESR-NDUFS2 mice using an ultracentrifugation-based cell fractioning protocol (Pascual et al., 2009) with minor modification. In brief, kidney was disrupted at 4°C with cold hypotonic buffer (10mM MOPS, 85mM sucrose, pH 7.2) in a Dounce homogenizer, mixed with an equal volume of hypertonic buffer (30mM MOPS, 250mM sucrose, pH 7.2), and centrifuged at 1000 g for 15 min at 4°C. The supernatant was centrifuged at 100,000 g for 1 h at 4°C. The pellet (mitochondrial fraction) was dissolved in lysis buffer (30mM Tris-HCl, 2M thiourea, 7M urea, 4%w/v

CHAPS, pH 8.5) and the supernatant corresponded to the cytosolic fraction. Forty μg of protein of each fraction, as determined with the RC DC protein assay (BioRad), were run on a Mini-PROTEAN® TGX Stain-Free™ Precast Gel (BioRad) and followed by immunoblotting as mentioned above. Total protein amount of each sample was used to normalize the amount of protein input in order to perform relative quantifications. Cell fractioning was validated by the expression of α -tubulin (cytosolic) and Vdac (mitochondrial).

Measurement of Mitochondrial Complex I and II Activities and Oxygen Consumption

Mitochondria were isolated from mouse kidneys and maximum enzymatic activities of MCI and mitochondrial complex II (MCII) were measured with a spectrophotometer as previously described with minor modifications (Birch-Machin and Turnbull, 2001; Fernández-Vizarra et al., 2002; Díaz-Castro et al 2012). Mitochondria were freeze-thawed 3 times in order to disrupt the membrane. Ten to twenty μg of the resulting sub-mitochondrial particles were used to estimate NADH-ubiquinone oxidoreductase MCI activity, which was determined by measuring the rotenone-sensitive decrease in absorbance at 340 nm due to NADH oxidation at 30°C. Five to twenty μg sub-mitochondrial particles were used to estimate succinate-ubiquinone oxidoreductase MCII activity, as determined by measuring the decrease in absorbance at 600 nm due to 2,6-dichlorophenol-indophenol reduction, which was coupled to ubiquinone-1 reduction, at 30°C. Both MCI and MCII activities were normalized with the protein amount, as determined by Bradford assay (BioRad).

MCI and MCII activities were also determined by monitoring the rate of oxygen consumption in the presence of the complex-specific substrates with a Clark oxygen electrode (see Lapuente-Brun et al., 2013). Kidneys were homogenized in the homogenization medium (0.32 M sucrose, 1 mM EDTA, 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.4) at 4°C. After centrifugation (1000g, 5 min), mitochondria in the supernatant were pelleted by centrifugation (13000rpm, 2 min) and re-suspended in the respiration medium (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.4, 25 mM sucrose, 75 mM sorbitol, 100 mM KCl, 10 mM K_2HPO_4 , 0.05 mM EDTA, 5 mM MgCl_2 , 1 mg/ml BSA). O_2 consumption was measured by incubating mitochondria (100 μg) in 1ml of respiration medium containing 1mM ADP and 2mM inorganic phosphate followed by addition of specific respiratory chain complex substrates (MCI, 5mM pyruvate plus 5mM malate; MCII,

10mM succinate) at 37°C using Oxygraph Plus System (Hansatech Instruments). MCI-dependent O₂ consumption was calculated as the fraction sensitive to MCI inhibitor rotenone (2µM), and MCII-specific O₂ consumption was measured in the presence of rotenone and calculated as the fraction sensitive to antimycin A (2µM).

MCI Activity Dipstick Assay

MCI activity in the superior cervical ganglion (SCG) was determined using Complex I enzyme activity dipstick assay kit (abcam) following the manufacturer's instruction with minor modifications. SCGs pooled from 4 mice were homogenized in 100 µl extraction buffer followed by incubation on ice for 20 minutes. The homogenate was then centrifuged at 16000 g for 30 minutes and the supernatant was collected for the enzymatic assay. Eight µg of protein extract, which was determined using the BioRad protein assay (BioRad), were applied to measure the MCI activity. The signal on the dipstick was scanned with an image analyzer (ImageQuant LAS 4000mini, GE Healthcare) and the signal intensity was quantified using the ImageQuant TL software (GE Healthcare).

Amperometric Recording of Single Cell Catecholamine Secretion in Slices

CB slices were used to obtain reproducible single glomus cell responses to hypoxia (Pardal and López-Barneo, 2002). Mouse CB dissection, slicing, and culture, as well as the measurement of catecholamine secretion were performed as previously described (Piruat et al., 2004). AM slices were obtained following previously described methodologies (García-Fernández et al., 2007) and recorded 1-4 hours after slicing. Slices were transferred to a recording chamber and continuously perfused with a control solution containing (in mM): 117 NaCl, 4.5 KCl, 23 NaHCO₃, 1 MgCl₂, 2.5 CaCl₂, 5 glucose and 5 sucrose. In the high K⁺ solutions, NaCl was replaced with KCl equimolarly. The "normoxic" solution was bubbled with a gas mixture of 5% CO₂, 20% O₂, and 75% N₂ (O₂ tension ~145 mmHg). The "hypoxic" solution was bubbled with 5% CO₂, and 95% N₂ to reach an O₂ tension in the chamber of ~15 mmHg. The "hypercapnic" solution was bubbled with 20% CO₂, 20% O₂ and 60% N₂. The low glucose experiments were done exposing the cells to a glucose-free solution containing (in mM): 117 NaCl, 4.5 KCl, 23 NaHCO₃, 1 MgCl₂, 2.5 CaCl₂, and 10 sucrose. In the succinate experiments, sucrose was replaced with a mix of sodium succinate and succinic acid equimolarly. Osmolality of solutions was

~300 mosmol/kg and the pH was 7.4. All the experiments were carried out at ~36 °C. Secretory events were recorded with a 10 μm carbon-fiber electrode positioned under visual control. The cumulative secretion signal was the sum of the time integral of successive amperometric events (Pardal and López-Barneo, 2002). Amperometric currents were recorded with an EPC-8 patch-clamp amplifier (HEKA Electronics, Lambrecht/Pfaltz, Germany), filtered at 100 Hz and digitized at 250 Hz before storage on computer. Data acquisition and analysis were done with an ITC-16 interface (Instrutech Corporation, NY, USA) and PULSE/PULSEFIT software (HEKA Electronics). Secretion rate (femtocoulombs (fC)/min) was calculated as the amount of charge transferred to the recording electrode during a given period of time. Cells with a basal secretory activity were considered to be responsive to a specific stimulus when the secretion rate increased at least two-fold with respect to the value in basal conditions.

Patch Clamp Recordings in Dispersed Carotid Body Glomus Cells

To obtain individual cells, both CBs from each mouse were incubated at 37°C for 20 min in an enzyme solution (1 ml of PBS with 0.6 mg of collagenase II (Sigma), 0.3 mg of trypsin (Sigma), 10 U of elastase porcine (Calbiochem) and 50 μM CaCl_2). Then the tissue was teased apart with forceps and incubated again for 5 min. Finally cells were mechanically dispersed and plated on slivers of glass cover slips treated with poly-L-lysine and kept in culture medium, DMEM (Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium) with 10% fetal bovine serum, 1% penicillin/streptomycin, 1% L-glutamine, and 84 μU of insulin per ml) at 37 °C in a 5% CO_2 incubator before use.

Macroscopic ionic currents were recorded from dispersed mouse glomus cells using either the perforated patch or the whole cell configurations of the patch clamp technique as adapted to our laboratory (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2006; 2010). Patch electrodes (2.5-3 $\text{M}\Omega$) were pulled from capillary glass tubes (Kimax, Kimble Products), fire polished on a microforge MF-830 (Narishige). Voltage-clamp recordings were obtained with an EPC-10 patch clamp amplifier (Heka Elektronik) using standard voltage-clamp protocols designed with Patch Master software (Heka Elektronik). Unless otherwise noted, holding potential was -70 mV. Data were filtered at 10 kHz, digitized at sampling interval of 20 μs and stored on a Macintosh computer. Off-line data analysis was performed using Igor 6 and Patch Master Fit

(Heka Elektronik). All experiments were conducted at 30-33°C. Macroscopic Ca^{2+} , Na^+ , and K^+ currents were recorded in dialyzed glomus cells. The solutions used for the recording of whole-cell Na^+ and Ca^{2+} currents contained (in mM): external: 140 NaCl, 9 BaCl_2 , 2.5 KCl, 1 CaCl_2 , 10 HEPES, and 10 glucose; pH 7.4 and osmolality 300 mOsm/kg; and internal: 110 CsCl, 30 CsF, 10 EGTA, 10 HEPES, and 4 ATP-Mg; pH 7.2 and osmolality 285 mOsm/kg. The solutions used for the recording of whole cell K^+ currents contained (in mM): external: 140 NaCl, 2.5 KCl, 10 HEPES, 10 glucose, 2.5 CaCl_2 , and 4 MgCl_2 , pH 7.4; and internal: 80 potassium glutamate, 50 KCl, 1 MgCl_2 , 10 HEPES, 4 MgATP, and 5 EGTA, pH 7.2. Experiments designed to estimate the cell's resting potential and to measure the inward holding current were made using perforated patches with Amphotericin B (240 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the pipette solution, which contained (in mM): 70 K_2SO_4 , 30 KCl, 2 MgCl_2 , 1 EGTA, 10 HEPES, pH 7.2. The standard bath solution contained (in mM): 140 NaCl, 2.5 KCl, 2.5 CaCl_2 , 4 MgCl_2 , 10 glucose, 10 HEPES, pH 7.4. In Na^+ -free solutions prepared to study standing Na^+ currents, external 140 NaCl were replaced with 140 mM N-methyl D glucamine (NMDG) chloride. To perform experiments in "normoxic" and "hypoxic" conditions cells were continuously perfused with a solution containing (in mM): 117 NaCl, 4.5 KCl, 23 NaHCO_3 , 1 MgCl_2 , 2.5 CaCl_2 , 5 glucose, and 5 sucrose. The osmolality of the solution was 280 mOsm/kg. The "normoxic" solution was bubbled with a gas mixture of 5% CO_2 , 20% O_2 , and 75% N_2 (O_2 tension, ~145 mm Hg). The "hypoxic" solution was bubbled with 5% CO_2 and 95% N_2 to reach an O_2 tension in the chamber of ~15 mm Hg. Experiments of currents induced by hypercapnia (20% CO_2) were done with the same control solution bubbled with 20% CO_2 , 20% O_2 , and 60% N_2 .

Microfluorimetric Measurements

For cytosolic Ca^{2+} measurements glomus cells were first incubated in DMEM containing Fura 2-AM 2 μM (TefLabs MW 1002) and pluronic acid 1 $\mu\text{l}/2\text{ml}$ (F-127 20% in DMSO, Invitrogen) for 1 h at 37 °C in a 5% CO_2 incubator. For the experiments, a coverslip with loaded cells was placed on a recording chamber mounted on the stage of an inverted microscope (Axiovert 35, Zeiss) equipped with epifluorescence and photometry. Alternating excitation wavelengths of 340 and 380 nm were used, and background fluorescence was subtracted before obtaining the F340/F380 ratio

(Ureña et al., 1994). In the figures the relative changes in $[Ca^{2+}]$ for each experiment are given by the F340/F380 ratio. To estimate the values of resting $[Ca^{2+}]$ an *in vitro* calibration was performed (see Ureña et al., 1994). Fluorescence measurements were made from a cell-free solution of 5 μ M Fura-2 salt in 1mM Ca^{2+} (140 mM KCl, 10 mM HEPES, 1mM Ca and 0 EGTA) and 0mM Ca^{2+} (140 mM KCl, 10 mM HEPES, 0mM Ca and 10 EGTA) in order to get maximum and minimum ratios respectively. The ratios obtained were used in the equation $[Ca^{2+}] = K_d \beta [(R - R_{min}) / (R_{max} - R)]$, where R is the cell ratio in basal conditions, R_{min} = minimum ratio (0 Ca^{2+}), R_{max} = maximum ratio (1mM Ca^{2+}), β is the ratio of the intensity of fluorescence obtained at 380 nm in the 0Ca solution and at 380 nm in the 1mM Ca^{2+} ($\beta = F_{380max} / F_{380min}$), and K_d is the dissociation constant for Fura-2 salt- Ca^{2+} at 25°C given by TEFLabs ($K_d = 200$ nM). Cytosolic $[Ca^{2+}]$ signals were digitized at a sampling interval of 500 ms. All the experiments were performed at room temperature (~25°C).

Measurements of NAD(P)H autofluorescence were done using a non ratiometric protocol. NADH was excited at 360 nm and measured at 460nm. Background fluorescence was subtracted in all the experiments. To measure mitochondria reactive oxygen species (ROS) production we used a roGFP sensor targeted to either the mitochondrial intermembrane space or the cytosol as previously described (Dooley et al., 2004; Cannon and Remington, 2009; Waypa et al., 2010). The construct was incorporated into adenoviral vectors which were used to transfect CB slices in 2 ml complete culture medium containing 4 μ l of viruses from a stock (1.1×10^{12} viral particles /ml; Viraquest). Slices were kept in the incubator for >48 h to allow the ro-GFP expression before used for recording of ROS production. The resulting redox-sensitive protein has excitation maxima at 400 and 484 nm, with emission at 525 nm. In response to changes in redox conditions, roGFP exhibits reciprocal changes in intensity at the two excitation maxima and a ratiometric signal was obtained. Minimum and maximal levels of cell oxidation were estimated by addition of 1 mM dithiothreitol (DTT) and H_2O_2 (0.1 mM), respectively. In some experiments, CB slices transfected with roGFP viruses were incubated with 100 nM MitoTracker® Deep Red FM (Molecular Probes, invitrogen) for 45 minutes to label mitochondria.

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